

ANALYSIS OF LIFE SKILLS EDUCATION IN THE CONTENT OF URDU TEXTBOOK BY NATIONAL CURRICULUM AT ELEMENTARY LEVEL

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ABSTRACT

This research presents a qualitative content analysis of the Grade 8 Urdu textbook developed under the National Curriculum (2022), focusing on the integration of life skills based on the UNICEF MENA Life Skills Framework (2017). The analysis is guided by four major skill clusters: learning, employability, personal empowerment, and active citizenship. The textbook, consisting of 22 chapters covering diverse literary, moral, and social themes, was examined to investigate the presence and distribution of these life skills across its content. The objectives of the study were to explore how life skills are integrated into the textbook, to appraise their F distribution across chapters and topics, and to evaluate the textbook using the UNESCO (2010) guidebook on textbook research and analysis. Findings reveal that the textbook effectively incorporates all four life skill clusters, with strong emphasis on learning skills, personal empowerment, and active citizenship. The content is well-structured, age-appropriate, and aligned with national curriculum objectives. It included a balanced combination of literary and non-literary texts, along with reading, writing, and vocabulary exercises that support language development. Furthermore, the analysis confirmed that the textbook meets many criteria outlined in the UNESCO framework, particularly in terms of organization, relevance, and learner suitability. However, certain limitations were identified, including a lack of modern teaching strategies, limited focus on advanced critical thinking, and insufficient integration of innovative and practical activities. Despite these gaps, the textbook serves as an effective educational resource. With further improvements in these areas, it can better support the development of comprehensive language skills and 21st-century competencies among learners.

Key words: Life Skills, Content Analysis, Urdu Textbook, National Curriculum

Introduction

Class 8th Urdu book has been prepared according to the (National Syllabus 2022) and published under the Federal Ministry of educational professional training. The aim of this book is to develop the language skills, literary taste, critical thinking and morality among the learners. This

book was designed to develop the basic skills of language like reading, writing and speaking among the learners. New knowledge, evolving learning theories, and rising technology are all influencing how curriculum and the educational process are conducted. In this regard, 21st Century skills might be considered one of the

most recent curriculum improvements. According to Esther & Roger (2021) the majority of programs were put into place throughout adolescence, with a noticeable shift in emphasis from early behavioral and emotional skills to a broader variety of life skills in later years. A broad variety of emotional, psychological, and cognitive abilities to enhance self-regulation, make wise decisions, and create supportive social connections are what define life skills (UNICEF, 2019).

The emphasis has been on life skills and education systems worldwide, particularly in low- and middle-income countries should include 21st century skills into their curricula to meet the needs of 21st-century society. According to Nursabaha & Juhannis (2022) the Life Skills Education (LSE) Independence Curriculum has improved students' independence in both social and individual domains, such as problem-solving, self-care, and social consciousness, in UNICEF pilot junior high schools in Bone Regency. The idea of learning in the twenty-first century is associated with students' abilities to handle challenges in their everyday lives and future encounters. Previously, it was anticipated that students would exhibit altered behavior upon completion of training program.

Urdu is recognized as a national language of Pakistan. It is not only the sources of communication but it also represents the culture, history and civilization of Pakistan. That's why in the education system Urdu language and study about Urdu literature had great scope. In 2024, M Jamil, IR Chohan, and R Tabassum explain the textbook pays little emphasis to the growth of life skills and instead focuses on transmitting knowledge about Pakistani politics, history, and social structures. There is a lack of emphasis on the procedures that facilitate active learning and the development of practical skills. To encourage continuous education, it is advised that curriculum designers intentionally include life skills through interactive assignments, problem-solving exercises, and thought-provoking conversations. The aim was to analyze this book is to make evaluation about the setting objectives are being achieved or not. At the level of grade 8th

it is most important stage of student's education life because at this stage students move forward to learn and understand about the literary and thoughtful content in their education despite of learn just about language. By using this book students can introduces about different genres of literature like Poem, Stories, Essays and informative stories.

Objectives

1. To investigate the integration of life skills in Urdu textbook of Grades 8th by National Curriculum
2. To appraise the distribution of life skills across chapters, topics and sections in Urdu textbook grade 8th by National Curriculum.
3. To evaluate class 8th Urdu textbook based on UNESCO (2010) guidebook.

Conceptual Framework

For analyzing the Urdu textbook of class 8th, the present research study followed the UNICEF MENA framework (2017) consisting of the four life skills clusters with twelve core life skills. Four clusters are learning, employability, personal empowerment and active citizenship skills. The learning Skill clusters consists of life skills including creativity, problem-solving and critical thinking, whereas the employability cluster consists of life skills of cooperation, decision-making and negotiation. The personal empowerment cluster consists of life skills of self-management, communication and resilience while the active citizenship cluster consists of life skills of respect for diversity, participation and empathy (Initiative, 2017). Class 8th Urdu textbook content analysis based-on UNESCO guidebook (2010). According to UNICEF MENA Life Skills Framework (2017) here are four cluster skills with sub skills

1. Learning Skills (Learning to Know)

Focus: Cognitive development and thinking abilities. Critical Thinking: Ability to analyze information logically and make reasoned judgments. Creativity: Ability to generate new ideas and think in innovative ways. Problem

Solving: Ability to classify problems and opt out the possible solutions.

2. Employability Skills (Learning to Do)

Focus: Skills needed for work and productivity. Cooperation (Teamwork): Ability to work effectively with others toward shared goals. Negotiation: Ability to reach agreements through discussion and compromise. Decision Making: Ability to choose the best option among alternatives.

3. Personal Empowerment Skills (Learning to Be)

Focus: Self-awareness and emotional strength. Self-Management: Ability to regulate emotions, behavior, and time effectively. Resilience: Ability to cope with stress and recover from challenges. Communication: Ability to express ideas and feelings clearly and effectively.

4. Active Citizenship Skills (Learning to Live Together)

Focus: Social responsibility and participation. Respect for Diversity: Ability to value and accept differences among people. Empathy: Emotional capability to feel for other. Participation: Ability to actively engage in community and civic activities

LITERATURE REVIEW

Text book analysis play important role in the educational research. It might be consist on the content, teaching strategies, structure, language, instruction and fundamental values present in the books. Farihatul,et.al (2023) describes textbook is a primary sources for both teacher and student for teaching – learning process so it should be aligned with the curriculum standards and learner needs.so researcher stress that textbook can play important to achieve the learning outcomes. Book analysis focuses on to identify the strength and weakness of the book content. According to Shazia, et al. (2024) it is very important to add the practical, group activities and ICT in the textbooks to enhance the creativity and critical thinking skill among the students. (UNESCO&WHO, 2013, 1999)

describes daily life skills can enable the humans to develop their cognitive skills to face their daily life challenges and these daily life skills like, Decision-making, communication, critical thinking, problem-solving, and interpersonal skills, emotional intelligence, and resilience are a few examples of life skills. AS Remya, et al. (2018) describe content analysis allow the researcher to evaluate about content, structure, themes and patterns. This method allows both qualitative and quantitative examination of textual material. Development in linguistic skills Prevalence of Social and moral values Because of these aspects this book is not only for the sake of education but it can also bring positive change in learner's personality. This book is prepared under the (National Book Foundation Curriculum 2022) and the content of this book basically focus on these skills primarily Listening, Speaking, Reading, and Writing. According to Smith et al. (2004) life skills have been shown to improve social relationships and reduce aggression and social problems. In their research, Ramesh and Arshad (2004) demonstrated how life skills improve both mental and physical health. Additionally, it lessens actions that are harmful to oneself and society. It encourages pupils to act in a way that is beneficial to society. According to Albertyn et al. (2004) life skills enhance critical thinking and make an individual deserving of society.

As a result, the individual leads an active life, develops professional responsibility, and aids in future planning. Hendricks (1998) defined life skills as essentially the Targeting Life Skills Model, which explains that these are the abilities that enable an individual to lead a successful life. The individual is leading a fulfilling life and contributing to society. These skills support young people's physical and emotional well-being. These abilities also assist youth in making the best choices and moving on in their lives.

Activities related to life functions that help people reach their goals in life are also referred to as life skills. It gives you the opportunity to live a better life. To succeed in life, remember three things: love yourself, accept who you are, and be honest with yourself. Mannix (2009) defines life

skills as a group of competencies that include everyday living skills including budgeting, eating, shopping, cleaning, and problem-solving. The ability to solve problems is a crucial and active rational practice that encompasses all other domains. In order to improve people's quality of life, a number of scholars and researchers recommended that life skills-based curriculum be incorporated into the educational system. Additionally, it improves the educational system so that students can contribute to the advancement of society. The majority of the elements of our everyday lives, including ethics, leadership, accountability, adaptability, personal competency, self-direction, and social skills, are included in life skills. These abilities aided in problem-solving and goal-achieving (Myers, 2010).

According to Wing (2013) of the Ministry of Education, life skills are explained as one of the key disciplines of study in various nations worldwide. In Pakistani schools, life skills education has never been taught on a regular basis. In order for the children to benefit from our curriculum, life skills must be included.

The main goal of teaching life skills is to provide students with plans that help them lead successful lives. Life skill education is a crucial curriculum for young people because it helps them recognize who they are, what they can do better, and how to evaluate their skills. Life skills training are necessary for young people to make responsible decisions, interact with others, and adapt to their environment. UNICEF (2012) defines life skills as a method of education that promotes and increases knowledge to help kids regain their abilities and attitudes by engaging in healthy activities.

With the use of life skills, we can transform teenagers into responsible adults. Everyday tasks including cooking, cleaning, shopping, obtaining a job, keeping a home, and driving are examples of life skills. The best method to learn these abilities is to practice them. Being physically active is crucial for a healthy existence. Taking care of your diet and maintaining good cleanliness are also crucial life skills (Kukreja, 2005).

Life-based skills, according to WHO (2009) are those abilities for good and adaptable behavior that allow people to successfully manage the responsibilities and demands of everyday life. Ten essential life skills were identified by the WHO Department of Mental Health: critical thinking, creativity, self-awareness, decision-making, empathy, problem-solving, interpersonal relationships, effective communication, emotion management, and stress management.

These eleven abilities are separated into three primary categories: Thinking skills are those that enhance the mind's capacity for logical analysis, critical and creative thought, problem-solving, and decision-making. Communication, interpersonal, leadership, advocacy, management, teamwork, and cooperation skills are all considered social skills. Emotional skills are those that allow a person to understand and be content on their own. Incorporate stress and emotion management, as well as personality management (Ravindra & Sharma et al., 2017).

According to Bouyssou et al. (2006) decision making is a process that involves gathering information, analyzing the data, identifying the problem, choosing the preferred option, and working on the decision. Taylor et al. (1994) defined problem-solving as the process of inquiry, result, and challenge resolution. Overcoming obstacles and finding the best answer are the goals of problem solving. Problem resolution involves a number of processes, including (1) problem identification, (2) problem definition, (3) problem formulation, (4) information organization, (5) resource allocation, (6) progress monitoring, and (7) outcome evaluation (Taylor et al., 1994).

Paul et al. (2008) defined critical thinking as evaluating and analyzing thinking with an understanding to improve skill. Increasing human performance requires effective communication. Since every person is unique, effective communication is essential. Each person has a unique personality and speaking patterns (Mortensen, 2008). The primary goals of life skills are to promote flexibility, raise knowledge of societal issues, empower people, and allow them

to voice their opinions. Additionally, it facilitates their involvement in life-affecting decisions.

Methodology

The Urdu textbook of 8th class was analyzed in the context of life skills using the qualitative content analysis method. Qualitative content analysis follows the procedure of generating codes, classes and themes followed by certain rules (Büyüköztürk et al., 2013). According to Yildirim et al. (2011) the content examination process, themes are generated from collected data and presented meaningfully to readers. (Kyngas, et.al, 2020) describe large amounts of textual data can be interpret by using this method systematically to find the themes and patterns. According to Mayring et al. (2014) it is useful method to analyze the content and learning outcomes of textbook and themes. Class 8th Urdu textbook content analysis based-on UNESCO guidebook (2010).The purposive sampling technique was used for selecting the textbook Urdu class 8th that can be downloaded from link: [//studyplusplus.com/fbise/books/8/urdu](http://studyplusplus.com/fbise/books/8/urdu)

Data Analysis

The content of this Text book (Class 8th Text book 2022) is established in diverse and organized manners. It has been added to several literary infinity so learners can brightened by different aspects of Urdu literature. The detailed class 8th Urdu textbook analysis based-on UNESCO guidebook (2010) on textbook research and textbook analysis is presented below:

Textbook Sector Components

The textbook components are as follows.

- **Front page:** The front page of the book is interactive and colorful. There is a picture of historical place (Khyber Pass) and on the top of height Pakistan's flag is waving and combination of green and white colure makes it identical. Furthermore, inner page has national anthem along-with the picture of Quaid-e-Azam.
- **Table of contents:** This section spans four pages and contain fourteen chapters.

- **Chapters.** Chapter 1 is (حمد) Chapter 2 is (اسوہ کامل کی روشنی میں والدین کا (نعت)Chapter 3 is (عبدالستار ایدھی)Chapter 4 is (احترام) Chapter 5 is (عبدالقدیر خان)Chapter 6 is (نشان حیدر)Chapter 7 is (مکار لومڑی) Chapter 8 is (ملی نغمہ) Chapter 9 is (مادرملت) Chapter 10 is (قانون کی گرفت) Chapter 11 is (ریل کا سفر) Chapter 12 is (منشیات کے اثرات) Chapter 13 is (وادی سوات کی (غزل)Chapter 14 is (علامہ اقبال کا تصور شاہین)Chapter 15 is (سیر) Chapter 16 is (حقیقت حسن)Chapter 17 is (پاک چین (کھیلوں کے عالمی Chapter 18 is (دوستی (Chapter 19 is (شام رنگین)Chapter 20 is (مقابلے)Chapter 21 is (دعا)Chapter 21 is (ماحولیات) and at the end (دعا) by Allama Iqbal was also added. Moreover, the table of content has been extended to include explanations relating vocabulary, reading and thinking skills, grammar and structure, writing skills and communication skills for all the chapters.

- **Textbook price & Number of Pages:** Price is Rupees 220 and total pages are 118.

- **Authors of the textbook:** The authors of the textbook are renowned personalities having professional expertise in the teaching of Urdu as a subject in various schools and colleges across Punjab. Authors are; Dr. Shafaqat Janjua; M. Shaheen Bloch Malgani; and Prof. Amjad Iqbal. This is a comprehensive textbook designed to facilitate and instruct class Eighth students. The main purpose of this textbook is to provide students with challenging and stimulating learning opportunities in-order to acquire command of Urdu language. This textbook, as it has been explained earlier that it follows the guidelines of National Curriculum 2022 of Federal Government of the Pakistan.

- **Approach:** This textbook assimilates the different aspects of Urdu language by following curriculum guidelines stated earlier in this document. This book involves different learning techniques which improve students 'skills by focusing on individual and group work. Moreover, these activities also help the student to respect diverse opinions and overcome the differences to approach for better solution as a team and at the same time students also gain confidence in expressing themselves.

- **Pre-reading:** The pre-reading section of the textbook introduce students to the learning objectives of the subject and aid their own experiences opinions and ideas to the discussion. This section add new knowledge as well as extend the existing ones. The activities provided in this section also facilitate teacher to evaluate the level of verbal skill conquered by each student.

- **Reading Text:** This textbook has both literary and non-literary texts. The knowledge of the world has been provided to the students in the non-literary text, however poems and stories are the part of literary text. While reading: The textbook provide multiple learning opportunities for the students while reading it. These activities facilitate in identifying the patterns of the different categories of text through skimming, scanning, making inference, deducing meaning from content, inferred meaning and generating queries for text understanding, while reading questions to predict, connect, question, visualize, assess, review and respond are designed for the students to interact with the text.

- **Vocabulary:** The vocabulary section provided at the start and end of each chapter is designed in a manner that provide opportunity to the students to explore the use and purpose of word root, contextual clues, phrases, transitional devices, similes, compound words, etc. the variety of vocabulary exercises provided at chapter end also exposes students to wide range of vocabulary which encourages them to have confidence in exploring and using new vocabulary. These exercise build up vocabulary as well as equip students to make new sentences in Urdu language.

- **Reading and Thinking Skills:** Independent learners normally rely on their thinking skills to enhance their study skills. Therefore, this section of the textbook of English will provide an opportunity to 8th grade students to be able to develop independent thinking skills. In this section greater emphases has been on thinking creatively, stories facts and opinions, determining consequences, defining alternative ideas, understanding and interpreting texts by applying critical thinking are the approaches which will assist students considerably in

academic and social life. Additionally, class 8th students will answer literal, factual, interpretive, inferential, evaluative, personal response and open ended questions. These activities are designed to enhance learning activities of grade 8th students in terms of individual and group level work activities.

- **Grammar:** This section of the Urdu textbook provides contextualized exercises on a specific grammar items to inspire student to apply their knowledge of the rules pertaining to the grammar in use. These rules are meant to make class 8th students understand and use principles of pronunciation, grammar, punctuation and syntax for developing accuracy in their spoken and written communication.

- **Writing Skills:** The writing skills of students are important in their academic and professional life. Therefore, greater emphases has been exerted on this aspect by introducing activities in the chapters that will significantly enhance the writing skills of the class 8th students. These activities are pertaining to the development of fluency and accuracy, academic, transactional and creative writing which emphasize on purposeful writing process which includes; brainstorming, mind mapping and interaction.

- **Oral Communication Skills:** The section of the Urdu textbook builds on the communication skills using selective linguistic exponents' in-order to communicate effectively for various functions of opinion, emotions, feelings and instructions in the real life events. This section of the chapter intend to develop effective communication skills in class 8th students which are demonstrated through dialogue, panel discussions, talks on particular topics, using conversations and dynamics of group discussion and interaction.

- **Teacher's Instructions:** In every chapter of the textbook it has been ensured that teacher is properly guided in terms of the main theme and direction of instructional material to be taught to the students. The main focus of this section is on the enhancement of student learning and the creation of learning environment in the classroom. These instructions develop teacher's repertoire of knowledge and

skills, and help them teach text and conduct related activities by involving students by keeping contextual realities in view. Moreover, teaching strategies of teacher are properly guided so as to make learning effective in terms of optimal

student learning experience in the class room as according to the guidelines of curriculum of Urdu language and National educational policy frameworks.

Analysis of Content

The detailed analyses of content provided in the Urdu textbook is as follows;

Table no 1:

Sr, no	Chapter Title	Theme	Page no	MENA Cluster	Skill	Sub-Skills
1	حمد	Divine forces	8 to 11	Personal Empowerment		Self-awareness, Values
2	نعت	Respect & Love	12 to 14	Personal Empowerment		Empathy, Respect
3	اسواہ کامل کی روشنی میں والدین کا احترام	Moral values	15 to 20	Personal Empowerment		Empathy, Self-management
4	عبدالستار ایدھی	Social service	21 to 25	Active Citizenship		Participation, Empathy
5	ڈاکٹر عبدالقدیر خان	Science & nationalism	26 to 29	Learning Skills		Critical Thinking
6	نشان حیدر	Bravery	33 to 37	Active Citizenship		Responsibility, Participation
7	مکار لومڑی	Moral story	38 to 42	Personal Empowerment		Problem Solving, Self-management
8	ملی نغمہ (نظم)	Patriotism	43 to 46	Active Citizenship		Participation, Respect for diversity
9	مادر ملت	Leadership	47 to 50	Active Citizenship		Participation, Responsibility
10	قانون کی گرفت	Justice	51 to 55	Active Citizenship		Decision Making, Responsibility
11	ریل کا سفر	Experience	59 to 62	Learning Skills		Observation, Creativity
12	منشیات کے اثرات	Social issue	63 to 66	Personal Empowerment		Self-management, Decision Making
13	غزل	Literary expression	67 to 70	Learning Skills		Creativity
14	وادی سوات کی سیر	Nature & tourism	71 to 75	Learning Skills		Creativity, Observation
15	علامہ اقبال کا تصور شاہین	Philosophy	76 to 80	Learning Skills		Critical Thinking, Creativity
16	حقیقت حسن	Aesthetics	84 to 86	Learning Skills		Critical Thinking
17	پاک چین دوستی	International relations	87 to 90	Active Citizenship		Respect for diversity, Participation
18	کھیلوں کے عالمی مقابلے	Sports	91 to 94	Employability Skills		Cooperation, Teamwork
19	شام رنگین	Emotions	95 to 98	Personal		Emotional expression

				Empowerment	
20	بچے	Childhood	99 to 102	Personal Empowerment	Empathy
21	ماحولیات	Environment	102 to 109	Active Citizenship	Responsibility, Participation
	دعا	Spirituality	110	Personal Empowerment	Self-awareness, Value

This table shows about the content analysis (UNESCO (2010) guidebook.) and MENA life skills clusters and arrangement of the content in this book provide the opportunity to the learners to analyze their knowledge about the particular lesson by donning the exercise at the end. The objective of these exercises is to develop ability about the language and learner's understanding.

According to MENA frame work:

Learning Skills

Learning skills include critical thinking, creativity, and problem solving. The Urdu textbook encourages critical thinking among students through evaluating evidence, making links between concepts, and concluding. The textbook of class 8th promotes critical thinking by asking questions such as (سوشل میڈیا کے فوائد اور نقصانات کے بارے میں مکالمہ لکھیں اور دو دوستوں کے درمیان اس کو پیش کریں، سائبر کرائم یونٹ کی ذمہ داریوں معلومات اکٹھی کریں اور کلاس میں تبصرہ کریں)

Page no (55). However writers can include more content that develop the critical thinking and one other example that is related to the creativity (کوئی مزاحیہ واقع اپنے الفاظ میں لکھیں، نظم کا خلاصہ) Page no (62) problem solving skills , This question related to problem solving skills (سبق منشیات کا استعمال : اگر آپ کو اسکول سے چھٹی کے بعد کوئی مشکوک شخص نظر آئے تو آپ کیا کریں گے؟، طلبہ کو ٹولوں میں تقسیم کریں اور ہر ٹولی کو ایک نکتہ فراہم کریں اور ان کے درمیان گفتگو کروائیں اور مطلوبہ حل نکلائیں (منشیات کی روک تھام میں والدین، تعلیمی اداروں اور حکومت کا کیا کردار ہے اس پر گفتگو کروائیں)

These question can develop the skills but more activities are needed to make the development more efficient. Because these question requires analysis, interpretation and personal response and it promote the critical thinking.

Employability Skills

Employability skills include life skills of writing, communication and organization. Questions like (نظم کا خلاصہ اپنے الفاظ میں لکھیں، درخواست یا خط تحریر کریں، مضمون لکھیں (محنت کی برکات) Page no 5, 18, and 78

Personal Skills

Personal empowerment include life skills self-aware, confidence and values. Questions like this (بر طالب علم اپنے پسندیدہ درخت، پودے یا پھول کے بارے میں اظہار خیال کرے، محکمہ جنگلات کے آفیسر کو خط لکھیں اور بتائیں کہ آپ پودے لگانا چاہتے ہیں اور آپ نے اس کے لیے بیس رضا کار تیار کیے ہیں اور وہ اس کے لیے پودے فراہم کریں) ، کھیل معاشرتی اقدار کو فروغ دیتے ہیں اس موضوع پر اسمبلی میں تقریر کریں) Page no (109, 94) these type of question can empower the personal skills but writer should increase these type of activities for more improvement.

Active Citizenship Skills:

Active Citizenship Skills include empathy, respect for diversity and participation. Empathy is discussed in the textbook by these lessons like (ماحولیات) and (بچے) and the skill participation and diversity discussed in the lessons like (نشان) (مادرملت) and (حیدر، ملی نغمہ نظم) (پاک چین دوستی) and also focus on active citizenship skills.

Discussion.

According to McDonald et al. (2016) described most schools use the text book to teach the Urdu subject. And textbook is the reflection of curriculum goals.so it is very important textbooks should maintain high quality to achieve the set objectives. The present study analyzed the Urdu textbook of class 8th of national curriculum (2022) in the context of life skills through qualitative analysis based on four clusters of life

skills learning, employability, personal empowerment and active citizenship with life skills under each cluster.

The Urdu textbook contain 21 chapters covering various themes, list of lessons, content explanation, exercises, key words, open and closed handed questions, subjectivity help the students to think in context of creativity. Örnek et al. (2024) also described that openhanded questions help the students to think critically. Textbook play active role to shape the curriculum and teacher practices (Aldahmash et al., 2016).

The Urdu textbook encourages learning skills that include critical thinking, creativity. It also promotes the critical thinking by using the philosophical concepts and creates the sense of active citizenship by using the content about relations of countries. To improve the problem solving skills conceptual questions are included in book. Örnek & Alaam (2024) described that textbook should promote review based questions to increase the problem solving skills. (Jamil et al., 2024) discuss in study activities should be plan step wise to help the learner to improve the problem solving skills and critical thinking. Regarding this study textbook focus on the employability skills but it is very important increase the question about these skills. There were some dilemmas that improve the decision-making skills in learner should be included in book. (Hansen et al., 2018) stated that book have several purpose such as framing teaching, disseminating content, setting projects, supplying a framework for activities, providing home tasks, and facilitating teachers.

Personal empowerment such as self-awareness, values these skills are addressed in the book by using content like giving different situations, and questions. Communications skills are also have been encouraged by group discussion, debates, and dialogues. (Zajkov et al., 2017) also claimed that textbooks are an essential source of knowledge that teachers and students mostly use but there are certain concerns about the quality of textbooks.

Active citizenship is also promoted through topics related to national identity, social responsibility, and community awareness.

Although employability skills are included, they appear comparatively less emphasized and require further strengthening, particularly in areas such as teamwork, problem-solving, and practical decision-making.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the analysis of the Grade 8 Urdu textbook (National Curriculum 2022) demonstrates that the content integrates life skills in alignment with the UNICEF MENA Life Skills Framework (2017). The study tell us that all four clusters—learning, employability, personal empowerment, and active citizenship—are present within the textbook, fulfilling the main objectives of the research. The distribution of these skills across 22 chapters reflects a thoughtful and structured approach, ensuring that students are exposed to a variety of cognitive, social, and moral learning experiences.

The textbook supports the development of learning skills through literary and comprehension-based activities, while personal empowerment is enhanced through moral, religious, and character-building content.

Moreover, the evaluation based on the UNESCO (2010) guidebook highlights that the textbook is well-organized, age-appropriate, and aligned with curriculum standards. It effectively incorporates reading, writing, and vocabulary exercises, contributing to overall language development. However, certain gaps remain, including limited use of modern teaching methodologies, insufficient focus on higher-order thinking skills, and a need for more engaging and activity-based learning approaches.

Recommendations

1. For learning more pictorial information may include in book.
2. Opportunities may provide to the students like Experimental and Project based learning.
3. Content that develop the critical thinking and problem solving skills among the learners may prefer in the book.

Although the book is in good manners but pictorial information have great impact on students

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